

Fault Diagnosis for a Class of Nonlinear Uncertain Hybrid Systems

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Abstract

This paper presents a fault diagnosis architecture for a class of hybrid systems with nonlinear uncertain time-driven dynamics, measurement noise, and autonomous and controlled mode transitions. The proposed approach features a hybrid estimator based on a modified hybrid automaton framework. The fault detection scheme employs a filtering approach that attenuates the effect of the measurement noise and allows tighter mode-dependent thresholds for the detection of both discrete and parametric faults while guaranteeing no false alarms due to modeling uncertainty and mode mismatches. Both the hybrid estimator and the fault detection scheme are linked with an autonomous guard events identification (AGEI) scheme that handles the effects of mode mismatches due to autonomous mode transitions and allows effective mode estimation. Finally, the fault isolation scheme anticipates which fault events may have occurred and dynamically employs the appropriate isolation estimators for isolating the fault by calculating suitable thresholds and estimating the parametric fault magnitude through adaptive approximation methods. Simulation results from a five-tank hybrid system illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Hybrid systems, fault diagnosis, hybrid automata, filtering, modeling uncertainty

1. Introduction

The reliable and smooth operation of large-scale systems, such as power systems and water systems, is of paramount importance and relies heavily on the use of real-time monitoring and fault diagnosis methods. Most of these engineering systems are usually best represented as hybrid systems that consist of discrete operating modes, each having its time-driven dynamics [1, 2]. As a result, traditional fault diagnosis methods for either time-driven or discrete-event systems (e.g., [3–7]) are unable to handle the combined time-driven and discrete-event dynamics of hybrid systems. Specifically, the fault diagnosis of hybrid systems presents a significant challenge since it requires the estimation of the hybrid state that consists of interlink continuous and discrete state variables. Moreover, it involves the diagnosis of faults in the time-driven dynamics part (i.e., parametric faults) and the discrete-event dynamics part (i.e., discrete faults).

Several interesting and innovative model-based approaches have been proposed in the literature to address the problem of fault diagnosis in hybrid systems. Some of the proposed approaches focus on diagnosing only parametric faults or only discrete faults, while some other approaches can diagnose both types of faults. In general, the fault diagnosis approaches for hybrid systems rely heavily on the ability to correctly estimate the hybrid state of the system, especially the mode of the system. For instance, in [8], the authors use parity residuals and derive for each system mode Analytical Redundancy Relations (ARRs), which allow them to estimate the system mode and diagnose both types of faults. In [9], ARRs and discrete automata are employed for the hybrid state estimation and the diagnosis of discrete faults. The authors in [10] also

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use ARRs for mode estimation, while [8, 9] consider the case of hybrid systems with nonlinear time-driven dynamics and emphasizing on diagnosing mainly parametric faults. In [11], the authors develop global ARRs (GARRs) for mode estimation and also quantitative fault detection and isolation (FDI) scheme for diagnosing both types of faults. However, the approach is mainly suitable for small-scale systems since it does not scale well for large-scale systems. In [12], the authors develop a bank of hybrid residual generators based on ARRs that allows the mode estimation of the system and diagnosis of both types of faults under some sufficient solvability conditions.

Another approach has been proposed in [13–15] where Hybrid Bond Graphs (HBGs) and Extended Kalman Filters (EKFs) are used for hybrid state estimation while qualitative analysis schemes are used for fault diagnosis of only parametric faults. These approaches avoid pre-enumeration of all possible modes at a system level by considering the modes at a component level, making them suitable for hybrid systems with a large number of modes. This property is also present in [16], where the authors proposed a hybrid estimation scheme using probabilistic hybrid automata and EKFs. Although the approach considers the presence of unknown modes, it can diagnose only discrete faults. This drawback is addressed in [17], where the approach in [16] is combined with structural residual analysis methods to diagnose both types of faults. However, despite the improvement, some parametric faults can be missed. In [18], a hybrid systems fault diagnosis approach is presented that uses analytic redundancy methods to identify the operating mode of the system, while hybrid minimal structurally overdetermined (HMSO) sets are defined for residual generation and diagnosis of parametric faults. Also, in [1], a qualitative fault isolation approach for diagnosing both types of faults in hybrid systems is developed using the structural model decomposition method. In [19], the authors use the hybrid automaton framework and develop algorithms to track the system mode. Then, consistency indicators are generated for each mode to diagnose both types of faults in hybrid systems with linear time-driven dynamics. Lastly, in [20], the authors extend the work in [15] by introducing discrete fault signatures to develop a compact framework that can diagnose both types of faults in hybrid systems. However, the approach can suffer from high false alarm rates in case of unknown measurement noise and modeling uncertainties.

In general, an important issue that is often neglected in all approaches mentioned earlier is the presence of modeling uncertainty. Specifically, due to modeling uncertainty, estimating the hybrid state of the system and diagnosing faults without having false alarms is challenging, especially when measurement noise and autonomous mode transitions exist (i.e., mode transitions triggered due to continuous state values). Although in some of the previously mentioned approaches modeling uncertainty is represented as zero-mean Gaussian noise, in practical systems, modeling uncertainty is typically unstructured or takes the form of an unknown nonlinear function. To the best of our knowledge, the problem of fault diagnosis for hybrid systems where the modeling uncertainty has the form of an unknown nonlinear function has received little attention in the available literature.

Specifically, in [21] a fault diagnosis approach is presented for hybrid systems with uncertain model parameters. The approach uses Kalman Filters that run in parallel (one for each system mode) and the orthogonal principle that helps with mode estimation and fault diagnosis in the presence of modeling uncertainty. The approach, although it considers multiple faults (i.e., faults occurring simultaneously), it can diagnose parametric faults with known magnitudes and is suitable for hybrid systems with stochastic transitions and linear time-driven dynamics. In [22], the authors propose a fault diagnosis approach for hybrid systems with nonlinear time-driven dynamics, autonomous and controlled mode transitions, and modeling uncertainty. The approach develops an observer that includes a continuous state observer, based on an unknown input-output EKF observer (UIEKO), and a mode observer consisting of a bank of mode isolators (one for each mode in the system including fault modes), each of which is a UIEKO. All isolators are activated once a mode change is detected, with the task to identify the new mode, either healthy or faulty. Although this approach is promising, activating isolators for all the modes of the system (healthy and faulty) and also the need for pre-enumeration of all modes *at a system level*, makes the approach suitable for systems with a small number of modes. Moreover, the approach does not take into consideration the presence of measurement noise which can affect the fault detection and isolation, as explained in [23].

The primary objective of this paper is the design of a comprehensive fault diagnosis architecture that overcomes the above-mentioned limitations for a class of hybrid systems with nonlinear time-driven dynam-

ics, autonomous and controlled mode transitions, measurement noise, and modeling uncertainty, that can diagnose both parametric and discrete faults while guaranteeing no false alarms. This work extends our earlier work in [24],[25] and makes the following contributions:

1. A generalized autonomous guard events identification (AGEI) scheme is developed that: (a) identifies promptly potential autonomous guard events before they occur in the system and adjust the detection thresholds accordingly so that false alarms, due to mode mismatch, are prevented in the fault detection scheme, and (b) detects the occurrence of autonomous guard events promptly and triggers them in the hybrid estimator, allowing effective mode estimation.
2. The filtering approach devised in [26] for discrete-time systems is extended for the case of nonlinear uncertain hybrid systems. Specifically, the filtering was incorporated into the detection scheme for detecting not only faults in the time-driven dynamics part as in [26] but also faults in the discrete dynamics part. Moreover, rigorous analytical results for detectability/isolability conditions in the context of uncertain hybrid systems are presented. Lastly, a new elegant formulation based on filtering notation is adopted compared to the convolution summation used in [26] to derive the detection threshold, providing a simple and intuitive presentation for the whole filtering approach.
3. A fault isolation scheme that uses the filtering approach is developed which anticipates possible faults and dynamically employs only the necessary isolation estimators for efficient fault isolation utilizing an exclusion based isolation logic and suitable thresholds. Moreover, the isolation scheme can approximate the magnitude of parametric faults.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the problem formulation and the hybrid systems modeling framework used in this work. Section 3 presents the proposed hybrid systems fault diagnosis architecture and discusses in detail all its components. Section 4 illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach with simulation results from a five-tank hybrid testbed system and, finally, Section 5 provides some concluding remarks.

2. Hybrid Systems Modeling and Problem Formulation

Let us consider a hybrid system \mathcal{S} that consists of N subsystems \mathcal{A}_I , $I \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, each having several modes of healthy and faulty operation. We model individual subsystems as *open hybrid automata (OHA)* since each subsystem model includes inputs and outputs. The overall system is the composition of those open hybrid automata that operate in parallel and interact via interconnection variables. We refer to the model for the overall system as *composition Open Hybrid Automaton (cOHA)*. Fig. 1 illustrates an example of a hybrid system \mathcal{S} that consists of two subsystems. The system is represented by a *cOHA* which is composed of two *OHA*s that interact via interconnection variables and include healthy and faulty modes.

Figure 1: Example of a *cOHA* composed of two *OHA*s.

Each subsystem *OHA* can be seen as an extension of a finite-state machine (FSM) that incorporates nonlinear uncertain discrete-time difference and algebraic equations for each mode to capture the time-driven dynamic evolution of a subsystem. More specifically, based on [16, 27], we describe the *OHA* for the

subsystem A_I , $I \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ as a tuple

$$\mathcal{A}_I := \langle \mathbf{s}_I, Q_I, \mathbf{w}_I, F_I, \eta_I, \Phi_I, \Sigma_I, \gamma_I, S_{I,0} \rangle \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{s}_I = \{q_I\} \cup \mathbf{x}_I$ is the hybrid state, composed of the operation mode (discrete state) $q_I \in Q_I$ and the continuous state variables $\mathbf{x}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$, where n_I is the dimension of continuous state vector,
- $Q_I = \{m_{I1}, \dots, m_{IN_{q_I}}\}$ specifies a finite set of $N_{q_I} = N_{h_I} + N_{\mathcal{F}_I}$ operation modes where: N_{h_I} denotes the healthy operation modes $Q_h \subset Q_I$ (solid line circles in Fig. 1), and $N_{\mathcal{F}_I} = N_{p_I} + N_{d_I}$ denotes the faulty operation modes $Q_{\mathcal{F}} \subset Q_I$, from which N_{p_I} are parametric fault modes $Q_p \subset Q_{\mathcal{F}}$ (dash and dot line circle in Fig. 1) that represent faults in the time-driven dynamics part (e.g., leakage in a tank), and N_{d_I} are discrete fault modes $Q_d \subset Q_{\mathcal{F}}$ (dash line circle in Fig. 1) that represent faults in the discrete event dynamics part (e.g., valve stuck close),
- $\mathbf{w}_I = \mathbf{u}_I \cup \mathbf{z}_I \cup \mathbf{y}_I$ is the set of I/O variables, that aggregates the inputs $\mathbf{u}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{r_I}$, the interconnection variables $\mathbf{z}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{c_I}$ that establish interconnections with other subsystems, and the outputs $\mathbf{y}_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$,
- $F_I : Q_I \mapsto F_{DE} \cup F_{AE}$ specifies the time-driven dynamics evolution in terms of nonlinear discrete-time difference equations F_{DE} (with sampling-period T_s) and algebraic equations F_{AE} , where both incorporate the effects of *local uncertainty* η_I ,
- $\Phi_I : Q_{\phi} \mapsto F_I$ specifies a set of parametric fault functions $\Phi_I = \{\phi(q_I^1, \mathbf{x}_I, \mathbf{z}_I, \mathbf{u}_I), \dots, \phi(q_I^{N_{p_I}}, \mathbf{x}_I, \mathbf{z}_I, \mathbf{u}_I)\}$ where the $\phi(q_I^{p_I}, \cdot)$ function describes the structure of the parametric fault at the p_I -th parametric fault mode $q_I^{p_I} \in Q_p$, $p_I \in \{1, \dots, N_{p_I}\}$,
- $\Sigma_I = G_a \cup G_c \cup \mathcal{F}$ is a set of events that consists of (see also Fig. 1):
 - a) *autonomous* guard events $g_a \in G_a \subset \Sigma_I$ where each one is triggered by a continuous state x value, based on some enabling condition represented by an inequality of the form $x \triangle \xi_a$, with $(x, \xi_a) \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\triangle \in \{\leq, \geq, =, <, >\}$,
 - b) *control* guard events $g_c \in G_c \subset \Sigma_I$ where each one is triggered by an input variable u value, based on some enabling condition that is represented by an inequality of the form $u \nabla \xi_c$, with $(u, \xi_c) \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\nabla \in \{\leq, \geq, =, <, >\}$, and finally
 - c) *fault* events $\varphi \in \mathcal{F} \subset \Sigma_I$,
- $\gamma_I : Q_I \times \Sigma_I \rightarrow Q_I$ are the transition functions labeled by events that trigger transitions between modes. Specifically, functions labeled by guard events g_a or g_c (autonomous or controlled, respectively) trigger transitions between healthy modes (solid arrow lines in Fig. 1). Transition functions labeled by fault events φ trigger transitions from healthy to parametric or discrete fault modes (dash arrow lines in Fig. 1),
- $S_{I,0}$ denotes the initial hybrid state $\mathbf{s}_0 = \{q_0\} \cup \mathbf{x}_0$.

The overall system is modeled by the *cOHA* \mathcal{S} that specifies the parallel composition of the set of subsystems automata $\mathcal{A} := \{\mathcal{A}_1, \dots, \mathcal{A}_N\}$. In other words, the *cOHA* represents the concurrently operating subsystems automata that interact via interconnection variables as introduced in [16], and it is characterised as a tuple

$$\mathcal{S} := \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{y}, \eta, \mathbf{v} \rangle, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, \dots, u_r]^T$ are the input variables and $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_n]^T$ are the output variables of *cOHA*, aggregated from each subsystem A_I to single vectors and re-indexed by the mapping functions¹ M_u :

¹For example, in Fig. 1 the two subsystems *OHA*s, each with inputs $\mathbf{u}_1 = \{u_1\}$ and $\mathbf{u}_2 = \{u_1, u_2\}$ and outputs $\mathbf{y}_1 = \{y_1, y_2\}$ and $\mathbf{y}_2 = \{y_1\}$, will result in a *cOHA* with aggregated and re-index inputs $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_1 \cup \mathbf{u}_2 \xrightarrow{M_u} [u_1, u_2, u_3]^T$ and outputs $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}_1 \cup \mathbf{y}_2 \xrightarrow{M_y} [y_1, y_2, y_3]^T$, respectively, as shown.

$\{1, \dots, r_I\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, r\}$ and $M_y : \{1, \dots, n_I\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, n\}$, respectively. Note that in the mapping functions, r and n denote the dimension of the aggregated input and output vectors, respectively. η is the mode dependent nonlinear function that denotes the overall *uncertainty* of the system, which acts on the continuous states $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_1 \cup \dots \cup \mathbf{x}_N$, while $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the measurement noise.

The *cOHA* describes the time-driven dynamics evolution of the whole system using the following set of mode-depended discrete-time difference equations with time step k ($t = T_s k$):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k) + \phi(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = \{q_1, \dots, q_N\}$ is the system mode (as a collection of the subsystems modes $q_I \in Q_I$), and $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_n]^T$ are the system continuous states aggregated from each subsystem \mathcal{A}_I and re-indexed using the mapping function $M_x : \{1, \dots, n_I\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, n\}$. \mathbf{y} is the measured output of the system that is corrupted by the measurement noise \mathbf{v} which is considered to be bounded. $f : Q \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^r \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ is a nonlinear function representing the mode-depended time-driven dynamics of the system and is derived by symbolically solving the subsystems' equations according to the mode \mathbf{q} . The symbolic solution essentially means eliminating the interconnection variables \mathbf{z} and replacing them with the respective subsystem's equations based on the current mode to get the monolithic system dynamics described by the nonlinear function $f(\cdot)$. $\eta : Q \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{N} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the overall mode-dependent *uncertainty* of the system. The term $\phi(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$ denotes the parametric fault function, which becomes nonzero in the case of a fault event in some subsystem \mathcal{A}_I , causing a transition to some parametric fault mode $q_I^{p_I} \in Q_{p_I}$. The system mode in this case is denoted as \mathbf{q}^p , where the system index p and the subsystem index p_I are related by the mapping function $M_p : \{1, \dots, N_{p_I}\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, N_p\}$, so that $p = M_p(p_I)$. The fault isolation task in this work relies on the consideration that the parametric fault function in the p -th mode is of the form

$$\phi(\mathbf{q}_k^p, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) = [(\theta_1^p)^T g_1(\mathbf{q}_k^p, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k), \dots, (\theta_n^p)^T g_n(\mathbf{q}_k^p, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]^T, \quad (4)$$

where, for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $p \in \{1, \dots, N_p\}$, $g_i(\mathbf{q}_k^p, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) : Q_p \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^r \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ are *known* functions that provide the "structure" of the parametric fault, and $\theta_i^p \in \Theta_i^p \subset \mathbb{R}^{Q_i^p}$ are *unknown* parameter vectors that represent the magnitude of the parametric fault. In this paper, for the sake of simplicity and without loss of generality, the parameter domains Θ_i^p are assumed to be origin-centred hyper-spheres with radius $M_{\Theta_i^p}$.

The objective of this work is to develop a monitoring and fault diagnosis architecture for a hybrid system of the form \mathcal{S} . Specifically, the proposed architecture, by considering the presence of autonomous mode transitions, modeling uncertainty η and measurement noise \mathbf{v} , can: (a) estimate the system's hybrid state from the values of input variables \mathbf{u} and the noisy measurement values of output variables \mathbf{y} ; (b) detect the occurrence of a fault event $\varphi \in \mathcal{F}$ that can transition the system to some discrete or parametric fault mode, and finally (c) isolate the occurred fault event, while in the case of a transition to a parametric fault mode, approximate the value of the unknown parameter vector θ .

The following assumptions are used throughout the paper:

Assumption 1. No multiple fault events occur exactly at the same time step.

Assumption 2. The hybrid system's continuous state variables \mathbf{x} remain bounded in a set \mathcal{X} before and after the occurrence of a fault event, that is $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathcal{X} \forall k \geq 0$.

Assumption 3. Each component of the overall modeling uncertainty η in (3) is an unstructured and unknown nonlinear function of $\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k$, and k , but it is bounded by some known functional $\bar{\eta}_i$, i.e.,

$$|\eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)| \leq \bar{\eta}_i(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k) \quad (5)$$

for all system modes $\mathbf{q}_k = \{q_{1,k}, \dots, q_{N,k}\}$ and for all $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n, \mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^r, i = 1, \dots, n$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Assumption 1 indicates that fault events occur in the system sequentially and at different time steps. Assumption 2 guarantees the boundedness of the continuous state variables before and after the occurrence of

a fault event and, subsequently, the stability of the system. Note that, in this work, we do not explicitly deal with the control problem; we only consider the fault diagnosis problem by using the inputs and outputs of the system; thus, this assumption is reasonable. Assumption 3 describes the class of modeling uncertainties under consideration that can be bounded with *a priori* known bounds in all operating modes of the hybrid system. Note that the bound given in (5) is quite general and allows great flexibility to the designer to select a suitable bound based on the system. For instance, an easy to use bound would be a bounding constant $\bar{\eta}_i$ which constitutes a more conservative option with respect to the bound given in (5).

3. Hybrid Systems Monitoring and Fault Diagnosis Architecture

The proposed monitoring and fault diagnosis architecture for nonlinear uncertain hybrid systems is depicted in Fig. 2 and consists of four parts: (a) the hybrid estimation module, (b) the fault detection module, (c) the autonomous guard events identification (AGEI) module and, (d) the fault isolation module.

Figure 2: Proposed fault diagnosis architecture for hybrid systems.

In brief, the hybrid estimation module is responsible for the hybrid state estimation and the fault detection module is responsible for detecting the occurrence of fault events. The AGEI module is responsible for two tasks: (a) to identify promptly potential autonomous guard events before they occur in the system, and adjust the detection thresholds in the fault detection module, so that false alarms due to mode mismatch are prevented, and (b) to trigger autonomous guard events in the hybrid estimator. Finally, the fault isolation module is activated once a fault is detected and it is responsible for isolating the occurred fault event, by dynamically employing fault isolation estimators (FIEs) for only the possible faulty modes and by utilizing an exclusion based isolation logic.

In the following sections, we describe each part in detail, and we derive analytical results for fault detectability and isolability, which implicitly indicate the classes of faults that can be detected and isolated, respectively.

3.1. Hybrid State Estimation

The hybrid estimation module is also a *cOHA* since it is a parallel composition of the set of subsystems OHAs $A := \{\mathcal{A}_1, \dots, \mathcal{A}_N\}$, where each A_I , $I \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is as given in (1)², and it is represented as a tuple

$$\mathcal{E} := \langle A, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{g}_a, \hat{\mathbf{q}}, \hat{\mathbf{x}} \rangle, \quad (6)$$

²The OHAs for the hybrid estimation module don't include any modeling uncertainty η as the OHAs for the system.

where the hybrid estimator inputs are the input vector \mathbf{u} and output vector \mathbf{y} from the system and also the autonomous guard events \mathbf{g}_a which are identified and triggered by the AGEI module. The hybrid estimator outputs are the estimates for the system mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and the continuous state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The main task of the hybrid estimation module is to address the following hybrid state estimation problem:

Problem 1 (Hybrid state estimation). Given the initial hybrid state \mathbf{s}_0 , the values for inputs \mathbf{u}_k and the noisy measured outputs \mathbf{y}_k of the system and the values of autonomous guard events \mathbf{g}_a from the AGEI module, estimate the hybrid state $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k \cup \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ at each time step k , where $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \{\hat{q}_{1,k}, \dots, \hat{q}_{N,k}\}$ with each $\hat{q}_{I,k} \in Q_{hI}$, $I = \{1, \dots, N\}$.

The hybrid estimator addresses the problem through mode estimation and estimation of the continuous state as follows:

3.1.1. Mode estimation

Each *OHA* \mathcal{A}_I in the hybrid estimator includes transition functions between healthy modes, i.e., $q_{I,i} = \gamma_I(\sigma_I, q_{I,j})$ $i \neq j$, labeled by autonomous guard events $\sigma_I = g_{aI} \in G_{aI}$ and controlled guard events $\sigma_I = g_{cI} \in G_{cI}$ as described in (1). The hybrid estimator estimates the system mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \{\hat{q}_{1,k}, \dots, \hat{q}_{N,k}\}$ at each time step k by:

- (a) tracking transition functions labeled by control guard events, i.e., $\hat{q}_{I,k+1} = \gamma_I(g_{cI}, \hat{q}_{I,k})$, in each subsystem *OHA* of the hybrid estimator, and
- (b) executing any transition functions labeled by autonomous guard events, i.e., $\hat{q}_{I,k+1} = \gamma_I(g_{aI}, \hat{q}_{I,k})$, that are triggered by the AGEI module in each subsystem *OHA* of the hybrid estimator.

For instance, in the hybrid system shown in Fig. 1, if the estimated system mode at time step k is $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = [m_{11}, m_{21}]^T$ and the AGEI module identifies that the autonomous guard event g_{a1} has occurred, then the hybrid estimator in its *OHA* \mathcal{A}_2 will execute the transition from mode m_{21} to mode m_{22} . Thus, the mode estimate at the next time step will be $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k+1} = [m_{11}, m_{22}]^T$.

3.1.2. Continuous state estimation

The hybrid estimator estimates the continuous state values using the following nonlinear estimation model:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = f(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k), \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k$ is the estimated system mode, \mathbf{y}_k is the measured noisy output and \mathbf{u}_k are the system inputs. Finally, f is obtained automatically by symbolically solving the set of equations from the *OHA*s based on the estimated system mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \{\hat{q}_{1,k}, \dots, \hat{q}_{N,k}\}$, i.e.,

$$F(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k) = F_1(\hat{q}_{1,k}) \cup \dots \cup F_N(\hat{q}_{N,k}). \quad (8)$$

Remark 1. The hybrid estimation module capability of obtaining the nonlinear discrete-time function automatically for each operating mode of the system is very convenient since it prevents the need of pre-computing these functions for all possible mode combinations, something that can be a tedious task for large-scale hybrid systems. Moreover, this capability is also used by the fault isolation module to get the nonlinear discrete-time functions for all the possible faulty modes dynamically. Therefore, removing the need for having a precomputed bank containing the dynamic functions for all possible faulty modes.

3.2. Fault Detection

The fault detection scheme utilizes the filtering approach proposed in [26] for nonlinear uncertain discrete-time systems adapted for nonlinear uncertain hybrid systems. The use of filtering dampens the effect of measurement noise and allows the derivation of tighter mode-dependent detection thresholds, which enhances the detectability of smaller magnitude discrete and parametric faults. The fault detection scheme which is depicted in Fig. 3, is interconnected with the AGEI module that alters the nominal detection threshold, as it will be explained in the sequel.

Figure 3: Fault detection scheme.

3.2.1. Filtering Approach

To dampen the effect of measurement noise \mathbf{v}_k (see (3)), each measured output variable y_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ is passed through a filter $H(z)$, where $H(z)$ is a m -th order, asymptotically stable filter (poles lie inside the open unit disc $|z| = 1$) with proper transfer function

$$H(z) = \frac{d_0 + d_1 z^{-1} + d_2 z^{-2} + \dots + d_m z^{-m}}{1 + c_1 z^{-1} + \dots + c_m z^{-m}}. \quad (9)$$

In general, each y_i can be passed through a different filter but in this paper, without loss of generality and to simplify the presentation, we consider the same $H(z)$ for all the output variables. Also, note that the form of $H(z)$ given in (9), is quite general to allow the use of both Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) and Finite Impulse Response (FIR) types of digital filters. This gives great flexibility to design $H(z)$ using several available methods for designing FIR and IIR digital filters [28, 29]. In specific, the filter $H(z)$ must be designed based on the measurement noise characteristics so that the noise is dampened. A good start would be the use of a low pass filter for $H(z)$ since, generally, in real applications, the sensor noise is high frequency. The filtering is crucial for the proposed scheme since it allows the derivation of less conservative detection thresholds, which in practice enhances the fault detectability properties as discussed in [23, 26].

Based on $H(z)$ and for mathematical analysis purposes, we define the filter $H_p(z) = z^{-1}H(z)$ where $H_p(z)$ is also asymptotically stable since it comprises of the same poles as $H(z)$ with an additional pole at $z = 0$ (inside $|z| = 1$). Since the filters $H(z)$ and $H_p(z)$ (with impulse responses $h(k)$ and $h_p(k)$, respectively) are asymptotically stable, they are also BIBO stable. Therefore, for bounded measurement noise \mathbf{v}_k , the filtered measurement noise $\mathbf{v}_{F,k}$ can be also bounded as follows:

$$|v_{Fi,k}| \leq \bar{v}_{Fi} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (10)$$

where $v_{Fi,k} \triangleq H(z)[v_{i,k}]$ and \bar{v}_{Fi} are computable bounding constants, which we will use in the sequel. Note that, in general, the notation $y(k) = G(z)[x(k)]$ used in this work denotes the output $y(k)$ of any discrete-time signal $x(k)$ which is passed through a filter with discrete-time transfer function $G(z)$. In other words, $G(z)$ denotes the transfer function of a linear filter, where inside $[\cdot]$ is the input signal $x(k)$, while the filtered output is denoted by $y(k)$. This notation (i.e., $[\cdot]$) is commonly found in the area of adaptive control [30, 31].

3.2.2. Residual Signal Generation

As depicted in Fig. 3, to generate the residual error, we first filter the system's output and the estimator's (continuous) state estimates. Specifically, by filtering the output signal \mathbf{y}_k we obtain the filtered output:

$$\mathbf{w}_k \triangleq H(z)[\mathbf{y}_k] = H(z)[\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k] = H(z)[\mathbf{x}_k] + H(z)[\mathbf{v}_k]. \quad (11)$$

and by using $\mathbf{v}_{F,k} = H(z)[\mathbf{v}_k]$ and $H(z) = zH_p(z)$, then (11) becomes:

$$\mathbf{w}_k = zH_p(z)[\mathbf{x}_k] + \mathbf{v}_{F,k} = \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{zH_p(z)X(z)\} + \mathbf{v}_{F,k}, \quad (12)$$

where $X(z) = \mathcal{Z}\{\mathbf{x}_k\}$, with $\mathcal{Z}\{\cdot\}$ referring to the Z-transform and $\mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{\cdot\}$ referring to the inverse Z-transform. By adding and subtracting \mathbf{x}_0 and applying Z-transform's linearity property, (12) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}_k &= \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{zH_p(z)(X(z) - \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{x}_0)\} + \mathbf{v}_{F,k} \\ &= \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{H_p(z)z(X(z) - \mathbf{x}_0)\} + \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{zH_p(z)\mathbf{x}_0\} + \mathbf{v}_{F,k}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

By using the general unilateral Z-transform time advance property with one step ahead [29], i.e., $z(X(z) - \mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{Z}\{\mathbf{x}_{k+1}\}$, and by substituting \mathbf{x}_{k+1} with (3) *under fault-free operation* i.e., $\mathbf{q} \in Q_h$ and $\phi(\cdot) = 0$, the following is derived:

$$z(X(z) - \mathbf{x}_0) = \mathcal{Z}\{f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)\}. \quad (14)$$

By using (14) and the fact that $H(z) = zH_p(z)$, then (13) becomes

$$\mathbf{w}_k = \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{H_p(z) \cdot \mathcal{Z}\{f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)\}\} + \mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{H(z)\mathbf{x}_0\} + \mathbf{v}_{F,k}. \quad (15)$$

Based on the following Z-transform pair

$$h_p(k) * (f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)) \xleftrightarrow{\mathcal{Z}T} H_p(z) \cdot \mathcal{Z}\{f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)\},$$

where $*$ indicates the convolution operator, the first term on the right hand side of (15), i.e., $\mathcal{Z}^{-1}\{H_p(z) \cdot \mathcal{Z}\{f(\cdot) + \eta(\cdot)\}\}$, is simply the left part of the transform pair above, which denotes the output of the linear filter with transfer function $H_p(z)$ and input $f(\cdot) + \eta(\cdot)$, i.e., $H_p(z)[f(\cdot) + \eta(\cdot)]$. Thus, (15) can be written as:

$$\mathbf{w}_k = H_p(z)[f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)] + H(z)[\mathbf{x}_0 \cdot \delta(k)] + \mathbf{v}_{F,k}, \quad (16)$$

where $\delta(k)$ indicates the discrete delta function (i.e., $\delta(k) = 1$ for $k = 0$ and zero otherwise). Finally, (16) becomes

$$\mathbf{w}_k = H_p(z)[f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)] + h(k)\mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{v}_{F,k}. \quad (17)$$

By also filtering the hybrid estimator's $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ estimates for the continuous state given by (7), we obtain the filtered state estimate

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k \triangleq H(z)[\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k] \quad (18)$$

with initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbf{y}_0$.

By using the filtered output \mathbf{w}_k and the filtered continuous state estimate $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k$, the residual error to be used for fault detection is given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_k \triangleq \mathbf{w}_k - \hat{\mathbf{w}}_k. \quad (19)$$

This residual constitutes the basis of the fault detection scheme and it is readily computable from the equations (11), (7) and (18).

An alarm for a fault detection is raised when the absolute value of the residual signal $|r_{i,k}|$ crosses its corresponding detection threshold $\bar{R}_{i,k}$, i.e., $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{R}_{i,k}$ for some $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, as it is also shown in Fig. 3. In other words, a fault event that transitions the system to a discrete or parametric fault mode is said to be detectable (i.e., a detection decision can be made) and an alarm is raised when $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{R}_{i,k}$.

3.2.3. Detection Threshold

To derive a suitable nominal detection threshold we consider, in the absence of any fault events, the maximum effect of the modeling uncertainty on the residual signal, and that there are no mode mismatches due to autonomous guards events (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \mathbf{q}_k$ at all times). Using a similar procedure as in the derivation of (17), $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k$ from (18) satisfies:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_k = H_p(z)[f(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + h(k)\mathbf{y}_0. \quad (20)$$

Prior to a fault event at time $k < k_f$ (where k_f denotes the time that a fault event occurs), the residual error can be written by using equations (17), (20) and (19) as³:

$$\mathbf{r}_k = H_p(z)[\Delta f(\mathbf{q}_k, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, k)] + \mathbf{v}_{F,k} - h(k)\mathbf{v}_0 \quad (21)$$

where $\Delta f(\mathbf{q}_k, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ is the mismatch function given by:

$$\Delta f(\mathbf{q}_k, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) \triangleq f(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k). \quad (22)$$

By taking the absolute value of (21) component-wise and by using the triangle inequality we obtain for each $i = 1, \dots, n$:

$$|r_{i,k}| \leq |H_p(z)[\Delta f_i(\mathbf{q}_k, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)]| + |H_p(z)[\eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k, k)]| + |v_{F,i,k}| + |h(k)v_{i,k}|.$$

To derive a suitable threshold for $|r_{i,k}|$ stated above, we make the following assumption:

Assumption 4. The filtered mismatch function when $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \mathbf{q}_k$ is bounded as follows:

$$|H_p(z)[\Delta f_i(\mathbf{q}_k, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)]| \leq \bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ is a computable mode dependent bounding function.

Remark 2. Assumption 4 states that there exists a bound in the mismatch between the true and estimated states of the system. This is a reasonable assumption for the systems that we are considering, though, if it is not possible to compute this function analytically, the bound can be estimated through simulation.

Therefore, using Assumptions 3 and 4 and also $\bar{v}_{F,i}$ given in (10), the following detection threshold is derived:

$$\bar{r}_{i,k} = \bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) + \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)] + \bar{v}_{F,i} + |h(k)|\bar{v}_i, \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{H}_p(z)$ is a filter with impulse response $\bar{h}_p(t)$ that satisfies $\bar{h}_p(t) \geq |h_p(t)|$ for all $t \geq 0$ and can be selected using the methods discussed in [26]. Lastly the term $|h(k)|\bar{v}_i$ consist of $h(k)$ that is the impulse response of the filter $H(z)$, and \bar{v}_i that are computable bounding constants based on the measurement noise characteristics that can be found using $\bar{v}_i \geq |v_{i,k}|$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Note that, even for a conservative bounds \bar{v}_i , the term $|h(k)|\bar{v}_i$ affects the detection threshold only during the initial transient, because the impulse response $h(k)$ of a proper and asymptotically stable transfer function $H(z)$ converges to zero exponentially fast.

Remark 3. The detection threshold given in (24) is robust to modeling uncertainty and guarantees no false alarms when all assumptions are satisfied. At the same time, the sensitivity of the detection threshold is enhanced with the use of filtering since more “tight” mode-dependent detection thresholds are calculated (i.e., less conservative with respect to the non-filtering case), which allows the detection of both discrete and parametric faults with smaller magnitudes. The detection threshold given in (24) is used in the fault detection scheme by default, i.e., $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}$, for the case of no mode mismatches (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \mathbf{q}_k$). However, if the AGEI module identifies that an autonomous guard event is possible to occur, to guarantee no false alarms for the case of mode mismatch (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k \neq \mathbf{q}_k$), it calculates and sets a new detection threshold in the fault detection scheme i.e., $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$, as described in detail in Section 3.3.

³In the rest of the paper, when there is no risk of ambiguity and for the sake of simplicity, we will use compact notations like $\eta(\mathbf{q}_k, k) \equiv \eta(\mathbf{q}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)$ and $\bar{\eta}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) \equiv \bar{\eta}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, k)$.

3.2.4. Fault detectability analysis

This part, examines the fault detectability conditions of fault events using the proposed fault detection scheme. To derive these conditions, we recall Assumption 1 for no multiple fault events and for simplicity, we also consider that the fault event will not occur when the AGEI module expects an autonomous guard event. Thus, the threshold for detection is assumed to be always $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}$ given by (24). If this is not true and the fault event occurs when the AGEI module expects an autonomous guard event, then in the following analysis, the new threshold $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ needs to be considered. The following theorem summarises the detectability conditions for a fault event that occurs at some unknown time step $k = k_f$ and triggers a transition to a discrete or a parametric fault mode.

Theorem 1 (Fault Detectability). *If a fault event φ_ℓ occurs at time k_f and transitions some subsystem I to a faulty mode q_I^{ℓ} and thus the system to a faulty mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ (either parametric or discrete), it is guaranteed to be detected at the time step $k_d > k_f$ if the following condition is satisfied for some $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$:*

$$|H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_{k_d}^\ell, \mathbf{x}_{k_d}, \mathbf{u}_{k_d}) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_d}, \mathbf{y}_{k_d}, \mathbf{u}_{k_d})]| > \bar{r}_{i,k_d} + \bar{v}_{Fi} + |h(k_d)|\bar{v}_i \quad (25)$$

where in the case of a transition to a discrete fault mode $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell \in Q_d$ then $\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \triangleq f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, k)$ and in the case of a transition to a parametric fault mode $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell \in Q_p$ then $\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \triangleq f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, k) + \phi_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$. Moreover, in the case of a parametric fault mode, the fault detectability given in (25) is further simplified as:

$$|H_p(z)[\phi_i(\mathbf{q}_{k_d}^\ell, \mathbf{x}_{k_d}, \mathbf{u}_{k_d})]| > 2\bar{r}_{i,k_d}. \quad (26)$$

Proof. If a fault event occurs at time k_f , the residual in (19) at time $k > k_f$ satisfies:

$$r_{i,k} = H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,0}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (27)$$

By using the triangle inequality, the residual in (27) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} |r_{i,k}| &\geq |H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - |v_{Fi,k}| - |h(k)v_{i,0}| \\ &\geq |H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - \bar{v}_{Fi} - |h(k)|\bar{v}_i. \end{aligned}$$

For fault detection, the inequality $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{r}_{i,k}$ must hold for some $i = 1, \dots, n$, thus the detectability condition in (25) is obtained.

In general, in the case of a discrete fault mode $f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot) \neq f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$ and $\eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot) \neq \eta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$ because the system dynamics change drastically. In the case of parametric fault mode though, the fault corresponds to the function $\phi_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot)$ and the remaining functions $f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot)$ and $\eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot)$ remain the same as in the estimated healthy mode, i.e., $f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot) = f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$ and $\eta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \cdot) = \eta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$. Thus, (27) can be written as

$$r_{i,k} = H_p(z)[f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) + \phi_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,0}. \quad (28)$$

By using the triangle inequality and Assumptions 3 and 4, (28) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} |r_{i,k}| &\geq -\bar{\Delta}f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) - \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)] - \bar{v}_{Fi} - |h(k)|\bar{v}_i + |H_p(z)[\phi_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| \\ &\geq -\bar{r}_{i,k} + |H_p(z)[\phi_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| \end{aligned}$$

For fault detection, the inequality $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{r}_{i,k}$ must hold for some $i = 1, \dots, n$, thus the simplified detectability condition for a parametric fault mode in (26) is obtained. \square

The above theorem provides sufficient conditions and characterizes implicitly the faults that can be detected by the proposed fault detection scheme.

3.3. Autonomous Guard Events Identification

Some of the transitions between healthy modes occur because of autonomous guard events, i.e., $g_a \in G_a \subset \Sigma$, which are triggered by enabling conditions based on the continuous state values \mathbf{x} (see (1)). Since in the hybrid estimator only the measured outputs \mathbf{y} and the estimated continuous states $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ are available, which include measurement noise and modeling uncertainty, the hybrid estimation module can trigger the autonomous guard events at a different time than the system. Because of this, the hybrid estimator will be in a different mode than the system; i.e., there will be a mode mismatch (i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k \neq \mathbf{q}_k$), which can cause the residual in the fault detection scheme to cross the nominal detection threshold given in (24) and issue an alarm, not because of a fault event but because of an autonomous guard event.

To exclude the possibility of false alarms due to autonomous guard events and also to trigger these events effectively in the hybrid estimation module, an autonomous guard events identification (AGEI) scheme is proposed. Specifically, the AGEI scheme can identify which autonomous guard event is possible to be triggered in the system and accordingly calculates and alters the detection threshold in the fault detection scheme to guarantee no false alarms due to potential mode mismatch. Moreover, the AGEI scheme by exploiting the nominal threshold $\bar{r}_{i,k}$ and the autonomous guard events enabling conditions, can detect the occurrence of autonomous guard events in the system, and trigger them in the hybrid estimator.

To perform the above operations, the AGEI scheme uses the *AGEI Matrix* with a structure as shown in Table 1. Each row of the AGEI Matrix keeps for every autonomous guard event g_{aj} , $j = 1, \dots, n_{g_a}$ in the system the following: (a) the enabling mode q_{Ij} , which is the mode of subsystem I from which g_{aj} can be triggered, (b) the enabling condition $x_i \Delta \xi_{aj}$ that triggers g_{aj} , (c) the transition mode q_{Ij}^* , which is the mode that the subsystem I transitions after g_{aj} is triggered, and finally (d) the residual $r_i \forall i$ affected by g_{aj} . Moreover, similar to [32], we consider that there is a *dwel-time* τ_D between consecutive autonomous guard events. Thus, only one row in the AGEI Matrix can be activated at each time, which avoids the need for the AGEI scheme to monitor for the simultaneous triggering of multiple autonomous guard events.

Table 1: AGEI Matrix Structure.

Autonomous Guard Event	Enabling Mode	Enabling Condition	Transition Mode	Residual Affected
g_{aj}	q_{Ij}	$x_i \Delta \xi_{aj}$	q_{Ij}^*	r_i
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

where $\Delta \in \{\leq, \geq, =, <, >\}$

The AGEI scheme runs the AGEI algorithm shown in Algorithm 1 which at each time step k , takes as inputs (see line 1 in Algorithm 1) the estimated system mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k$ from the hybrid estimator, the filtered output \mathbf{w}_k given in (11), the residual signal \mathbf{r}_k given in (19) and the nominal detection threshold $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_k$ given in

Algorithm 1 Autonomous Guard Events Identification (AGEI)

- 1: **AGEI**($\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{w}_k, \mathbf{r}_k, \bar{\mathbf{r}}_k$) executed at each k time step
 - 2: **for each** g_{aj} in AGEI Matrix **do**
 - 3: **if** $\hat{q}_{I,k} = q_{Ij}$ **and** $\lambda(w_{i,k}, \Delta, \xi_{aj}) = 1$ **then**
 - 4: set $\bar{R}_{i,k} := \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ in fault detection scheme
 - 5: **if** $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{r}_{i,k}$ **then**
 - 6: trigger g_{aj} event in the hybrid estimator and
 - 7: keep $\bar{R}_{i,k} := \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ for the next K time steps
 - 8: **end if**
 - 9: **else**
 - 10: use $\bar{R}_{i,k} := \bar{r}_{i,k}$ in fault detection scheme
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: **end for**
-

(24). Then, to identify if an autonomous guard event g_{aj} is possible to occur in the system, for each event g_{aj} , $j = 1, \dots, n_{g_a}$ in the AGEI Matrix the algorithm makes the following two checks (see line 3): (a) if the current mode estimate $\hat{q}_{I,k}$ is equal to the enabling mode q_{Ij} of the event g_{aj} , and (b) if the function $\lambda(\cdot)$ returns 1. The first check is to determine if based on the current mode estimate the event g_{aj} is possible to occur. The second check is to determine if the event g_{aj} is possible to occur according to its enabling condition $x_i \Delta \xi_{aj}$. In more detail, the second check uses the function $\lambda(w_{i,k}, \Delta, \xi_{aj})$ that first calculates according to the constant ξ_{aj} from the g_{aj} enabling condition an upper bound Ξ_{aj}^+ and lower bound Ξ_{aj}^- using

$$\Xi_{aj}^\pm \triangleq (1 \pm \delta) |H(z)[\xi_{aj}]|, \quad (29)$$

where $\delta \in (0, 1]$ is a design parameter constant. Next, based on the bounds given by (29), the event's g_{aj} enabling condition operator Δ and its respective state $x_{i,k}$ filtered measurement value $w_{i,k}$ (i.e., $w_{i,k} \triangleq H(z)[y_{i,k}]$ as given in (11)), the function $\lambda(w_{i,k}, \Delta, \xi_{aj})$ returns 1 if the autonomous guard event g_{aj} is possible to occur in the system and 0 otherwise, by using the following decision rule:

$$\lambda(\cdot) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \Xi_{aj}^- \leq |w_{i,k}| \leq \Xi_{aj}^+ \text{ and } \Delta \in \{=\} \\ & \text{if } |w_{i,k}| \geq \Xi_{aj}^- \text{ and } \Delta \in \{>, \geq\} \\ & \text{if } |w_{i,k}| \leq \Xi_{aj}^+ \text{ and } \Delta \in \{<, \leq\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Note that, due to the unavailability of the continuous state \mathbf{x} , the enabling condition $x_i \Delta \xi_{aj}$ cannot be checked directly by AGEI. Therefore, the check is made using the output measurements by exploiting filtering for dampening the effect of noise. Explicitly, the decision rule in (30) relies on the filtered measurements $w_{i,k}$ and on the filtered value of ξ_{aj} . In addition, for taking into consideration the filtered noise and also the delay that filtering imposes, the design parameter constant $\delta \in (0, 1]$ is incorporated that determines the percentage to move Ξ_{aj}^+ up and Ξ_{aj}^- down from $H(z)[\xi_{aj}]$, as indicated by (29). With the introduction of δ , the AGEI scheme can promptly identify each autonomous guard event g_{aj} before it occurs in the system so that it can set a new detection threshold accordingly, avoiding any potential false alarms in the fault detection scheme. The value of δ is preferable to be set quite low, i.e., 1-5%, and can be further fine-tuned so that the use of the new detection threshold in the fault detection scheme is minimized.

The AGEI makes the above two checks for every g_{aj} and if one or both checks are false it means that the event g_{aj} will not currently occur in the system. Thus, AGEI continues to line 10, leaving the fault detection scheme to use the nominal detection threshold given in (24). However, if both checks are true, it means that g_{aj} is possible to occur in the system. Thus, AGEI continues to line 4 and it will set a new detection threshold $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ for any residual(s) affected by g_{aj} according to the AGEI Matrix. The new detection threshold is derived by following a similar procedure as in the derivation of (24) and is given by:

$$\bar{r}_{i,k}^* = \bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k) + \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i^*] + \bar{v}_{F_{i,k}} + |h(k)|\bar{v}_i, \quad (31)$$

where \mathbf{q}^* is the new mode that the system transitions if g_{aj} occurs (according to the AGEI Matrix), $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ is the *mode* mismatch bounding function that can be obtained similarly to Assumption 4, and finally the uncertainty bound $\bar{\eta}_i^*$ is given by:

$$\bar{\eta}_i^* \triangleq \max(\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k), \bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^*, k)).$$

Note, that $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ is the bound that takes into account the mode mismatch error between the system and the hybrid estimator due to the possible event g_{aj} such that $|H_p(z)[f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| \leq \bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$, where $\mathbf{q}_k^* \neq \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k$ and $f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \cdot) \neq f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$. Therefore, the bound $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}_k^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ is larger or equal than the bound $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, k)$ given in (23) where $\mathbf{q}_k = \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k$ and $f_i(\mathbf{q}_k, \cdot) = f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k, \cdot)$. Also, $\bar{\eta}_i^*$ is the maximum bound on the system uncertainty between either the current mode or the new mode that the system is possible to transition. Thus, the new detection threshold given in (31) is larger or equal than the nominal threshold, i.e., $\bar{r}_{i,k}^* \geq \bar{r}_{i,k}$ and guarantees no false alarms because of possible mode mismatches due to autonomous guard events.

Figure 4: Illustration of AGEI algorithm operation during an autonomous guard event g_{aj} with enabling condition $x_i = \xi_{aj}$ (i.e. $\Delta \in \{=\}$) where: (a) shows the actual mode q_I and estimated mode \hat{q}_I of subsystem I that g_{aj} occurs, (b) shows $|w_i|$ associated with the enabling condition of g_{aj} and, (c) shows the residual r_i and its corresponding threshold \bar{R}_i that are affected by g_{aj} .

Once the new detection threshold is set, the AGEI moves to line 5 to detect a mode mismatch due to g_{aj} . This is done by checking if the absolute value of the residual signal that is affected by g_{aj} has crossed its corresponding threshold, i.e., $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{r}_{i,k}$. If this becomes true, then it means that the g_{aj} has occurred in the system and it is detected by AGEI. Note that the nominal detection threshold $\bar{r}_{i,k}$ is calculated for the current estimated mode \hat{q}_k and not the new q_k^* thus, if the residual crosses this threshold it means that mode transition has occurred. In other words, when a mode transition occurs in the system, the residual will start to increase due to the function dynamics mismatch. During the mode mismatch, the new detection threshold $\bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ is suitably chosen in order to take into consideration this mismatch, and when the residual exceeds the nominal threshold $\bar{r}_{i,k}$ (which is based on no-mode mismatch), then a mode mismatched is detected without any false alarms. Hence once the mode mismatched is detected, AGEI triggers the event g_{aj} in the hybrid estimator (see line 6), allowing effective mode estimation. Once g_{aj} is executed in the hybrid estimator, AGEI keeps in the fault detection scheme the new threshold given by (31) for the next K time steps (see line 7). This is done to avoid any false alarms because of any transients in the residual signal which are picked up by the filters due to the mode transition. The number of time steps K can be calculated from the impulse response $h(k)$ of the selected filter $H(z)$ in the fault detection scheme. Specifically, K is equal to the number of time steps that the impulse response of $h(k)$ takes to converge to zero (or sufficiently close to zero in the case of IIR filter). After the K time steps are passed, AGEI switches the fault detection scheme to the nominal threshold, i.e., $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}$.

Fig. 4 illustrates an example of the AGEI scheme operation during an autonomous guard event g_{aj} with enabling condition $x_i = \xi_{aj}$ ($\Delta \in \{=\}$) to help understand better its operation. As can be seen in Fig. 4, before time k_1 , AGEI is not expecting g_{aj} ; thus it leaves the nominal threshold in the fault detection scheme. However, at k_1 (see ① in Fig. 4) AGEI expects g_{aj} to occur since the estimated mode for subsystem I is equal to the enabling mode of g_{aj} , i.e., $\hat{q}_{I,k_1} = q_{Ij}$, and also condition $\Xi_{aj}^- \leq |w_{i,k_1}| \leq \Xi_{aj}^+$ is true which meets the decision rule in (30) based on g_{aj} enabling condition. Since g_{aj} is expected, AGEI sets in the fault detection scheme (see ② in Fig. 4) the new threshold $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$, $k \geq k_1$, as given in (31) that guarantees no false alarms in case of a mode mismatch due to g_{aj} . After that, AGEI waits the detection of a mode

mismatch to trigger g_{aj} in the hybrid estimator. At k_2 , g_{aj} is triggered in the system; thus there is a mode mismatch between the system and the hybrid estimator, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k \neq \mathbf{q}_k$, which leads to the increase of the residual signal r_i . The mode mismatch is detected by AGEI at k_3 (see ③ in Fig. 4) since $|r_{i,k_3}| > \bar{r}_{i,k_3}$ and immediately triggers g_{aj} in the hybrid estimator (see ④ in Fig. 4). Thus, $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k = \mathbf{q}_k, \forall k > k_3$, which leads r_i to decrease. However, AGEI keeps the new threshold for the next K time steps (see ⑤ in Fig. 4) to avoid any false alarms due to transients picked up by the filters as explained earlier. After K time steps, at k_4 (see ⑥ in Fig. 4) AGEI switches the fault detection scheme back to the nominal threshold $\bar{R}_{i,k} = \bar{r}_{i,k}$.

Remark 4. The above procedure is followed by AGEI when an autonomous guard event is expected to occur. However, during the period that AGEI expects an autonomous guard event and the new threshold is set (i.e., between k_1 and k_4 as shown in Fig. 4) a fault event is also possible to occur that can affect AGEI decision. In this case, AGEI works with the fault detection scheme and the fault isolation scheme so that the fault event can be detected and isolated. Specifically, if a fault event occurs during the period $k_1 < k < k_4$ as shown in Fig. 4 two cases are possible: (a) the residual at some point might cross the new threshold i.e., $|r_{i,k}| > \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$ or (b) the residual at some point might cross the nominal threshold but remain below the new threshold i.e., $\bar{r}_{i,k} < |r_{i,k}| < \bar{r}_{i,k}^*$. In the first case, the Fault Diagnosis scheme will immediately issue an alarm, while in the second case, it will issue an alarm with some delay and specifically at $k \geq k_4$. In both these cases, AGEI will provide to the fault isolation scheme both the enabling mode q_{Ij} and the transition mode q_{Ij}^* . Thus, the fault isolation scheme will be able to check based on both these modes which faults might be possible to occur and employ the proper FIEs to isolate the fault, as discussed in the next section.

3.4. Fault Isolation

Once the fault detection scheme detects a fault at $k = k_d$, the fault isolation scheme is activated to isolate the occurred fault event. To accomplish this task, the fault isolation scheme based on the current mode, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_d}$ (or the modes provided by the AGEI scheme as explained in Remark 4), determines which fault events are possible to have occurred using the hybrid estimation module. Subsequently, it determines the possible faulty modes that each subsystem may have transitioned. For each possible faulty mode, discrete or parametric, a fault isolation estimator (FIE) is employed that estimates the faulty mode dynamics and also calculates adaptive thresholds which are used for the isolation decision.

Specifically, to isolate the faulty mode, and thus the occurred fault event, an exclusion based isolation logic is used. The residual of each employed FIE is compared with its corresponding isolation threshold, and a possible faulty mode is excluded when its residual becomes larger than its corresponding threshold. Thus, successful fault isolation occurs if the residual of the FIE associated with the actual fault remains below its corresponding threshold, while the residuals of all other FIEs become larger than their corresponding thresholds.

To derive the necessary thresholds for the FIEs, we first examine that the discrete-time dynamics of the system given in (3) after a fault event φ_ℓ occurs and transitions the system to some faulty mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ either discrete or parametric are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= \zeta(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k), \quad \forall k \geq k_f \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where in the case of a transition to a discrete fault mode $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell \in Q_d$ then $\zeta(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \triangleq f(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, k)$ and in the case of a transition to a parametric fault mode $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell \in Q_p$ then $\zeta(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \triangleq f(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, k) + \phi(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$ where $\phi(\cdot)$ is given in (4).

Given that at the time of detection k_d , from mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_d}$ there are transitions to N_s possible discrete or parametric faulty modes, then the same number of FIEs are employed (one for each possible fault mode), where the dynamics for the estimation of the continuous state for the s -th FIE, $s \in \{1, \dots, N_s\}$, $\forall k \geq k_d$ if it estimates a discrete fault mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}^s \in Q_d$ or parametric fault mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}^s \in Q_p$ are given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^s = \begin{cases} f(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) & \text{if } \hat{\mathbf{q}}^s \in Q_d \\ f(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \hat{\phi}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k^s) & \text{if } \hat{\mathbf{q}}^s \in Q_p \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

with initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k_d}^s = \mathbf{y}_{k_d}$. In the case that the s -th FIE estimates a parametric fault mode then the parametric fault function estimate is given by $\hat{\phi}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k^s) \triangleq (\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ (see (4)), which indicates the linearly-parametrized function that matches the structure of $\phi_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \cdot)$, while $\hat{\theta}_i^s \in \Theta_i^s$ denotes the unknown parameters that will be approximated online through a learning law (to be specified later on).

The challenge for the fault isolation scheme is to isolate both discrete and parametric fault modes, taking into account the modeling uncertainty and measurement noise. To deal with the measurement noise, the filtering approach that was implemented in the fault detection scheme is also employed in the fault isolation scheme to dampen the effect of measurement noise and allows the derivation of tighter thresholds for each FIE that eases the fault isolation task. Specifically, by using the same filter structure $H(z)$ as in (9), the residual error for the s -th FIE to be used for fault isolation is given by (similarly to (19)):

$$\mathbf{r}_k^s \triangleq H(z)[\mathbf{y}_k - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^s], \quad \forall k \geq k_d. \quad (34)$$

For the residual signal \mathbf{r}_k^s of each employed FIE, it is necessary to derive and use a suitable threshold $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_k^s$ that guarantees that if a discrete or parametric fault mode is matched by its corresponding FIE, then it will not be excluded. In the next subsections, we first derive suitable thresholds for both types of FIEs, and then conduct isolation analysis and provide sufficient conditions on what faults can be successfully isolated by the proposed scheme.

3.4.1. FIEs estimating discrete fault modes

By using (32) and (33) in a similar procedure as the derivation of (21) and with an initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k_d}^s = \mathbf{y}_{k_d}$, the i -th component of the residual error for the s -th FIE estimating a discrete fault mode is:

$$r_{i,k}^s = H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,k_d}. \quad (35)$$

If the discrete fault mode estimated by the s -th FIE matches the occurred fault mode, then $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell = \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s$ and $\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) = f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$. Recalling Assumptions 3 and 4 we can define the following threshold $\bar{r}_{d,i,k}^s$ for the s -th FIE estimating a discrete fault mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s \in Q_d$ (similar to (24)):

$$\bar{r}_{d,i,k}^s = \bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) + \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + \bar{v}_{Fi,k} + |h(k)|\bar{v}_i \quad (36)$$

that guarantees that if a discrete fault mode is matched by its corresponding FIE, then its residual will never cross its threshold and hence, it will not be excluded.

3.4.2. FIEs estimating parametric fault modes

By using (32) and (33) in a similar procedure as the derivation of (21) and with an initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k_d}^s = \mathbf{y}_{k_d}$, the i -th component of the residual error for the s -th FIE estimating parametric fault mode is:

$$r_{i,k}^s = H_p(z)[\zeta_i(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - (\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,k}. \quad (37)$$

where the s -th FIE approximates the unknown parameters $\hat{\theta}_i^s$ using the following learning law [33]

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s &= \begin{cases} \mu_{i,k} & \text{if } |\mu_{i,k}| \leq M_{\hat{\Theta}_i^s} \\ \mathcal{P}[\mu_{i,k}] & \text{if } |\mu_{i,k}| > M_{\hat{\Theta}_i^s} \end{cases} \quad (38) \\ \mu_{i,k} &:= \hat{\theta}_{i,k-1}^s + \frac{\gamma_0^s r_{i,k}^s}{\beta_0^s + \|g_i^s(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k-1)\|^2} g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k-1) \\ \mathcal{P}[\mu_{i,k}] &:= \frac{M_{\hat{\Theta}_i^s}}{|\mu_{i,k}|} \mu_{i,k} \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < \gamma_0^s < 2$ is known as learning rate and $\beta_0^s > 0$ is a design constant. $\mathcal{P}[\cdot]$ is the projection operation that modifies the standard learning law in order to prevent the adjustable parameters from drifting to infinity.

In the case the parametric fault mode estimated by the s -th FIE matches the occurred fault mode then $\mathbf{q}_k^\ell = \hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s$ and $\zeta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, k) = f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + (\theta_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \eta(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$, thus (37) becomes

$$r_{i,k}^s = H_p(z)[f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + H_p(z)[(\theta_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - (\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + H_p(z)[\eta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,k}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$r_{i,k}^s = H_p(z)[\Delta f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + H_p(z)[(\theta_{i,k}^s)^T \Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) + (\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + H_p(z)[\eta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + v_{Fi,k} - h(k)v_{i,k} \quad (39)$$

where $\Delta f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) \triangleq f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$ is the mismatch function as in (22), $\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s = \theta_{i,k}^s - \hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s$ is the fault parameter approximation error, and finally $\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$ is the fault structure mismatch function given by:

$$\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) \triangleq g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k). \quad (40)$$

By taking the absolute value of (39) and using the triangle inequality we obtain:

$$|r_{i,k}^s| \leq |H_p(z)[\Delta f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)]| + |H_p(z)[\eta_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)]| + \left| H_p(z)[(\theta_{i,k}^s)^T \Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) + (\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s)^T g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] \right| + |v_{Fi,k}| + |h(k)v_{i,k}|,$$

recalling Assumptions 3 and 4, the above equation satisfies

$$|r_{i,k}^s| \leq \bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) + \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + \bar{v}_{Fi,k} + |h(k)|\bar{v}_i + \|\theta_{i,k}^s\| |H_p(z)[\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)]| + \bar{H}_p(z)[\|\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s\| \|g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)\|]. \quad (41)$$

Note that, the right hand side of (41) cannot be used as a threshold since the values of $\theta_{i,k}^s$, $\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s$ and $\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$ are unknown. However, we can derive upper-bounds for all these quantities similarly as in [34]. Thus, $\theta_{i,k}^s$ can be upper-bounded by $\bar{\theta}_{i,k}^s \triangleq M_{\Theta_i^s}$ and $\tilde{\theta}_{i,k}^s$ can be upper-bounded by the function $\kappa_{i,k}(\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s) \triangleq M_{\Theta_i^s} + \|\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s\|$. Finally, since the fault structure mismatch function $\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$ is filtered, we can derive a suitable bound by making the following assumption (similar to Assumption 4):

Assumption 5. The filtered fault structure mismatch function is bounded as follows:

$$|H_p(z)[\Delta g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)]| \leq \bar{\Delta} g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (42)$$

where $\bar{\Delta} g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)$ is known computable bounding function.

Assumption 5 is similar to Assumption 2 and thus Remark 2 also applies. By using Assumption 5 and the bounds $\bar{\theta}_{i,k}^s$ and $\kappa_{i,k}(\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s)$ we can derive the following threshold \bar{r}_p^s for the s -th FIE estimating a parametric fault mode $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s \in Q_p$:

$$\bar{r}_{p,i,k}^s = \bar{\Delta} f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k) + \bar{H}_p(z)[\bar{\eta}_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)] + \bar{v}_{Fi,k} + |h(k)|\bar{v}_i + \|\bar{\theta}_{i,k}^s\| \|\bar{\Delta} g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, k)\| + \bar{H}_p(z)[\|\kappa_{i,k}(\hat{\theta}_{i,k}^s)\| \|g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)\|] \quad (43)$$

which guarantees that if a parametric fault mode is matched by its corresponding FIE, then its residual will not exceed its threshold and hence, it will not be excluded.

3.4.3. Fault isolation analysis

In this part, we provide sufficient conditions for the successful isolation of the occurred fault event. Although the derived thresholds given in (36) and (43) that guarantee that if the actual fault mode is matched by its corresponding FIE, it will not be excluded, unfortunately, because of uncertainty η , measurement noise and the fault parameters approximation error $\tilde{\theta}$ (in the case of estimating parametric fault modes), there is no assurance that all out of one of the employed FIEs will exclude their corresponding fault modes. However, it is possible to derive sufficient conditions for successful isolation by the proposed scheme, which are summarized in the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (Fault Isolability). *Given a fault event φ_ℓ that transitions the system to a fault mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ (either discrete or parametric) and at the time of fault detection k_d there are $s \in \{1, \dots, N_s\}$ possible parametric or discrete fault modes that the system can transition to, then if for each employed FIE $s \in \{1, \dots, N_s\} \setminus \{\ell\}$ there exist some time instant $k_s > k_d$ and some $i_s \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that the following conditions are satisfied*

In the case the s -th FIE estimates a discrete fault mode:

$$\left| H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_{k_s}^\ell, \mathbf{x}_{k_s}, \mathbf{u}_{k_s}) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_s}^s, \mathbf{y}_{k_s}, \mathbf{u}_{k_s})] \right| > \bar{r}_{d_{i_s, k}}^s + \bar{v}_{F_{i_s, k_s}} + |h(k_s)| \bar{v}_{i_s} \quad (44)$$

In the case the s -th FIE estimates a parametric fault mode:

$$\left| H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_{k_s}^\ell, \mathbf{x}_{k_s}, \mathbf{u}_{k_s}) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_s}^s, \mathbf{y}_{k_s}, \mathbf{u}_{k_s}) - (\hat{\theta}_{i_s, k_s}^s)^T g_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k_s}^s, \mathbf{y}_{k_s}, \mathbf{u}_{k_s})] \right| > \bar{r}_{p_{i_s, k}}^s + \bar{v}_{F_{i_s, k_s}} + |h(k_s)| \bar{v}_{i_s} \quad (45)$$

then the fault mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ and thus the fault event φ_ℓ will be isolated at time $\max_{s \in \{1, \dots, N_s\} \setminus \{\ell\}} (k_s)$.

Proof. Supposing that the fault event φ_ℓ has occurred which transitioned the system to the fault mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ (either discrete or parametric), the residual error for the case that the s -th FIE is estimating a discrete fault mode at $k > k_d$ using (32) and (33) is

$$r_{i_s, k}^s = H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{F_{i_s, k}} - h(k)v_{i_s, k}. \quad (46)$$

By taking the absolute value of (46) and using the triangle inequality we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |r_{i_s, k}^s| &\geq |H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - |v_{F_{i_s, k}}| - |h(k)v_{i_s, k}| \\ &\geq |H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - \bar{v}_{F_{i_s, k}} - |h(k)| \bar{v}_{i_s}. \end{aligned}$$

In the case that the s -th FIE estimates a discrete fault mode other than the occurred fault mode, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{q}}^s \neq \mathbf{q}^\ell$, then in order to be excluded, the inequality $|r_{i_s, k}^s| \geq \bar{r}_{d_{i_s, k}}^s$ must hold at some time instant $k_s > k_d$ for some $i_s = 1, \dots, n$, and hence the exclusion condition in (44) is obtained.

Similarly, the residual error for the case that the s -th FIE is estimating a parametric fault mode at $k > k_d$ using (32) and (33) is

$$r_{i_s, k}^s = H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - (\hat{\theta}_{i_s, k}^s)^T g_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)] + v_{F_{i_s, k}} - h(k)v_{i_s, k} \quad (47)$$

By taking the absolute value of (47) and using the triangle inequality we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} |r_{i_s, k}^s| &\geq |H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - (\hat{\theta}_{i_s, k}^s)^T g_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - |v_{F_{i_s, k}}| - |h(k)v_{i_s, k}| \\ &\geq |H_p(z) [\zeta_{i_s}(\mathbf{q}_k^\ell, \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - f_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) - (\hat{\theta}_{i_s, k}^s)^T g_{i_s}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_k^s, \mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)]| - \bar{v}_{F_{i_s, k}} - |h(k)| \bar{v}_{i_s}. \end{aligned}$$

In the case that the s -th FIE estimates a parametric fault mode other than the occurred fault mode, i.e., $\mathbf{q}^s \neq \mathbf{q}^\ell$, then in order to be excluded, the inequality $|r_{i_s, k}^s| \geq \bar{r}_{p_{i_s, k}}^s$ must hold at some time instant $k_s > k_d$ for some $i_s = 1, \dots, n$, and hence the exclusion condition in (45) is obtained. Combining both conditions above, we can conclude that for a successful isolation of the fault mode \mathbf{q}^ℓ and thus the fault event φ_ℓ , all FIEs $s \in \{1, \dots, N_s\} \setminus \{\ell\}$ have to exclude their corresponding fault modes at some time instants $k_s > k_d$ and some $i_s = 1, \dots, n$ which proves the fault isolability theorem. \square

4. Simulation Results

In this section, we present the effectiveness of the proposed approach with simulation results using the five-tank testbed system from [35]. The five-tank system is shown in Fig. 5 and in this work it is modeled as a hybrid system, considering both the time-driven dynamics and the discrete-events dynamics of the various constituent subsystems.

Figure 5: Five-tank hybrid system.

Specifically, the system (see Fig. 5) consists of twelve interconnected subsystems, three pumps P_j , $j = 1, \dots, 3$, four valves V_j , $j = 1, \dots, 4$, (V_1 & V_2 are supply valves and V_3 & V_4 are interconnection valves), and five tanks T_j , $j = 1, \dots, 5$. The system has two inputs u_1 and u_2 which prescribe the position (*Open/Close*) of the interconnection valves V_3 & V_4 , respectively, while it has five outputs y_i , $i = 1, \dots, 5$ which are the noisy measured values for the water level states x_i , $i = 1, \dots, 5$, of the five tanks. During normal operation, the three pumps and the two supply valves are responsible for filling their respective tanks automatically. Specifically, every pump and supply valve (i.e., V_1 & V_2) has its own internal sensor and logic controller and can automatically start supplying water to its respective tank when a predefined minimum level is reached and then stop when a predefined maximum level is reached. On the other hand, the two interconnection valves, V_3 and V_4 , are controlled by the system operator through the binary inputs u_1 and u_2 , respectively, to balance the tanks water levels if necessary.

In the five-tank system, several parametric and discrete faults are considered. Specifically, five parametric faults are considered, which represent leakages in all five tanks. Each tank can suffer from leakage due to a circular hole of unknown radius on the tank's bottom, which causes a leak outflow. Eleven discrete faults are also considered. Three of them denote permanent failures in each of the three pumps, making them unable to fill their respective tanks. The other eight discrete faults denote failures in the valves. Each valve can either stuck in the open position or stuck in the close position affecting its normal operation. All the faults are triggered by unobservable fault events that transition each particular subsystem to a parametric or discrete fault mode.

The hybrid estimation module for the five-tank system was developed according to Section 3.1, and its graphical representation is shown in Fig. 6. The hybrid estimator consists of twelve *OHA*s \mathcal{A}_I , $I = \{1, \dots, 12\}$, connected via interconnection variables, where each *OHA* models the healthy and faulty behaviors of each subsystem. In Fig. 6, to simplify the presentation, only four *OHA*s are shown (i.e., \mathcal{A}_1 for tank

Figure 6: The hybrid estimation module for the five-tank system.

Table 2: AGEI Matrix for Five-Tank System

Autonomous Guard Event	Enabling Mode q_I	Enabling Condition	Transition Mode q_I^*	Residual Affected
g_{a1}	m_{61}	$x_1 \leq X_{1min}$	m_{62}	r_1
g_{a2}	m_{62}	$x_1 \geq X_{1max}$	m_{61}	r_1
g_{a3}	m_{71}	$x_2 \leq X_{2min}$	m_{72}	r_2
g_{a4}	m_{72}	$x_2 \geq X_{2max}$	m_{71}	r_2
g_{a5}	m_{81}	$x_5 \leq X_{5min}$	m_{82}	r_5, r_1
g_{a6}	m_{82}	$x_5 \geq X_{5max}$	m_{81}	r_5, r_1
g_{a7}	m_{91}	$x_3 \leq X_{3min}$	m_{92}	r_3, r_1
g_{a8}	m_{92}	$x_3 \geq X_{3max}$	m_{91}	r_3, r_1
g_{a9}	m_{101}	$x_4 \leq X_{4min}$	m_{102}	r_4, r_2
g_{a10}	m_{102}	$x_4 \geq X_{4max}$	m_{101}	r_4, r_2

T_1 , \mathcal{A}_8 for pump P_3 , \mathcal{A}_{10} for the supply valve V_2 and \mathcal{A}_{11} for interconnection valve V_3). The rest OHAs are the same for similar subsystems but with different numbering for the modes and the transition events. Since the pumps and the supply valves automatically supply water to their tanks, their respective OHAs include autonomous guard events for transitioning between the healthy modes with enabling conditions as shown in the AGEI Matrix in Table 2. The two interconnection valves, on the other hand, have control guard events driven by the input values. The hybrid estimator includes sixteen fault events that transition the OHAs to either a parametric or discrete fault mode. Specifically, each of the fault events φ_j , $j = 1, \dots, 5$, triggers a parametric fault in each of the five tanks. Similarly, each of the fault events φ_j , $j = 6, \dots, 8$, triggers a discrete fault in each of the three pumps to permanently fail and stop supplying water to their respective tanks. Lastly, φ_j , $j = 9, 11, 13, 15$, trigger discrete fault transitions to each of the four valves to stuck in the closed position, while φ_j , $j = 10, 12, 14, 16$, trigger discrete fault transitions to each of the four valves to stuck in open position.

For all OHAs \mathcal{A}_I , $I = \{1, \dots, 12\}$ and their various modes $q_I \in Q_I$, the dynamics that are used by the hybrid estimator for estimating the continuous state, are given by the discrete-time difference equations F_I as follows (where superscripts p and d denote the dynamics of parametric and discrete fault modes, respectively):

1) For tanks OHAs \mathcal{A}_I , $I = 1, \dots, 5$, the F_I are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} F_I(m_{I1}) &= \{x_{i,k+1} = x_{i,k} + \frac{T_s}{A_i}(z_{I,k}^{in} - z_{I,k}^{out} - c_i S \sqrt{2gx_{i,k}}), z_{I,k} = x_{i,k}\} \\ F_I(m_{I2}^p) &= \{x_{i,k+1} = x_{i,k} + \frac{T_s}{A_i}(z_{I,k}^{in} - z_{I,k}^{out} - c_i S \sqrt{2gx_{i,k}}) + \phi_i(m_{I2}^p, x_{i,k}), z_{I,k} = x_{i,k}\}, \forall i = I, \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where x_i , $i = 1, \dots, 5$ denote the continuous states indicating the liquid level for each tank, A_i denote the cross-section areas for each tank, and T_s the sampling step. The variables c_i denote the flow coefficients for the outflow-pipes, S denotes the pipes cross-section area, and g the standard gravity coefficient. The variables $z_{I,k}^{in}$, $z_{I,k}^{out}$ are given at each time step k by

$$z_{I,k}^{in} = \begin{cases} z_{6,k}, & I=1 \\ z_{7,k} + z_{11,k}, & I=2 \\ z_{9,k}, & I=3 \\ z_{10,k} + z_{12,k}, & I=4 \\ z_{8,k}, & I=5 \end{cases} \quad z_{I,k}^{out} = \begin{cases} z_{8,k} + z_{9,k} + z_{11,k}, & I=1 \\ z_{10,k}, & I=2 \\ z_{12,k}, & I=3 \\ 0, & I=4,5 \end{cases}$$

where z_I , $I = 1, \dots, 12$, are the interconnection terms. Lastly, according to (4) the parametric fault functions, that denote a leak fault in each tank, are given by

$$\phi_i(m_{I2}^p, x_{i,k}) = \begin{cases} \theta_i^p \left(-\frac{T_s}{A_i} \pi \sqrt{2gx_{i,k}} \right) & \forall i = I \\ 0 & \forall i \neq I. \end{cases} \quad (49)$$

where $\theta_i^p = \rho_i^2$ and indicates the unknown parameter to be estimated, while ρ_i is the radius of the leak hole in each tank.

2) For pumps OHAs \mathcal{A}_I , $I = 6, \dots, 8$, the F_I are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} F_I(m_{I1}) &= F_I(m_{I3}^d) = \{z_{I,k} = 0\} \\ F_I(m_{I2}) &= \{z_{I,k} = 5 \times 10^{-6} \sin(0.1 \cdot k \cdot T_s) + 1.8 \times 10^{-4}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

3) For supply valves OHAs \mathcal{A}_I , $I = 9, 10$, the F_I are:

$$\begin{aligned} F_9(m_{91}) &= F_9(m_{93}^d) = \{z_{9,k} = c_s S \sqrt{2gz_{1,k}}\} \\ F_{10}(m_{101}) &= F_{10}(m_{103}^d) = \{z_{10,k} = c_s S \sqrt{2gz_{2,k}}\} \\ F_I(m_{I2}) &= F_I(m_{I4}^d) = \{z_{I,k} = 0\}, \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

where c_s denote the flow coefficient for the supply valves.

4) For the interconnection valves OHAs \mathcal{A}_I , $I = 11, 12$, the F_I are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{11}(m_{111}) &= F_{11}(m_{113}^d) = \{z_{11,k} = c_c S \text{sign}(z_{1,k} - z_{2,k}) \sqrt{2g|z_{1,k} - z_{2,k}|}\} \\ F_{12}(m_{121}) &= F_{12}(m_{123}^d) = \{z_{12,k} = c_c S \text{sign}(z_{3,k} - z_{4,k}) \sqrt{2g|z_{3,k} - z_{4,k}|}\} \\ F_I(m_{I2}) &= F_I(m_{I4}^d) = \{z_{I,k} = 0\}, \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where c_c denote the flow coefficient for the interconnection valves.

The hybrid automaton model for the actual system and the hybrid estimator along with the proposed fault diagnosis approach were implemented using Matlab and Simulink software. For the simulation of the hybrid estimator we use the following nominal parameter values: $A_1 = A_2 = 0.0573m^2$, $A_3 = A_4 = 0.0346m^2$, $A_5 = 0.0707m^2$, $c_1 = c_2 = 0.68$, $c_3 = c_4 = 0.4$, $c_5 = 0.7$, $c_s = 0.62$, $c_c = 0.37$, $S = 3.167 \times 10^{-5}m^2$, $g = 9.81 \frac{m}{s^2}$, $T_s = 0.01s$, $X_{Imin} = 0.1m$, for $I = 1, \dots, 4$, $X_{5min} = 0.05m$, $X_{1max} = X_{2max} = 0.4m$, $X_{3max} = X_{4max} = 0.35m$, $X_{5max} = 0.2m$. For the simulation of the actual system, however, we introduce

modeling uncertainty by adding inaccuracy to some of the above parameters values as follows: 5% in tanks cross-sectional areas A_i , 10% in all flow coefficients c_i , c_s and c_c and 20% in all outflow-pipes and valves cross-section areas S .

After suitable offline simulations with measurement noise 5% of the maximum state value, i.e., $\bar{v}_i = 0.02 m$, $i = 1, \dots, 5$, the filter $H(z)$ was selected as a 4th order Butterworth IIR low-pass filter with normalised cut-off frequency 0.2 (i.e., butter command in MATLAB). This type of filter $H(z)$ was selected mainly based on the noise characteristics so that the noise is dampened. Other filters of higher order can also be used. However, for this application, this filter was sufficient. A suitable filter $\bar{H}_p(z)$ was also selected as $\bar{H}_p(z) = \frac{0.35}{1-0.95z^{-1}}$. Using the aforementioned filter $H(z)$ the values for the various necessary bounds were found. Specifically, the filtered noise bound is $\bar{v}_{F_i} = 3 \times 10^{-7}$, $i = 1, \dots, 5$, the filter mismatch bound function is $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}, k) = 4 \times 10^{-7}$ for all $\hat{\mathbf{q}} \in Q$, the filtered mode mismatched bound function in (31) is $\bar{\Delta}f_i(\mathbf{q}^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}, k) = 3.5 \times 10^{-5}$ for all $(\mathbf{q}^*, \hat{\mathbf{q}}) \in Q_h$ and lastly, the bound for the filtered fault structure mismatch function is $\bar{\Delta}g_i(\hat{\mathbf{q}}) = 4 \times 10^{-7}$ for all $\hat{\mathbf{q}} \in Q_p$. The bound on the uncertainty function in all operating modes is calculated by $\bar{\eta}_i(\mathbf{q}_k, k) = |f_i(\mathbf{q}_k, k, \alpha_{max}) - f_i(\mathbf{q}_k, k, \alpha_{nom})|$, $i = 1, \dots, 5$, where α_{max} denote the model parameters values with maximum uncertainty and α_{nom} the model parameters values with nominal values. Also, the parameters for the AGEI scheme were set as $\delta = 0.001$ and $K = 40$. Finally, for the fault isolation scheme the parameters for the learning law were set as $\beta_0 = 1$ and $\gamma_0 = 1.5$ and the domain for the unknown parameters θ are set as origin-centred hyper-spheres with radius $M_{\Theta_p} = 1 \times 10^{-4}$. For all the simulation results the system initial hybrid state was $\mathbf{x}_0 = [0.3, 0.12, 0.15, 0.3, 0.09]^T$ and $\mathbf{q}_0 = [m_{11}, m_{21}, m_{31}, m_{41}, m_{51}, m_{61}, m_{71}, m_{81}, m_{91}, m_{101}, m_{111}, m_{121}]^T$.

Figure 7: Simulation results of a healthy run showing the mode estimation of pump P_3 during autonomous guard events and the effect on the fault detection scheme where: in Fig. 7(a) are the results with AGEI scheme disabled, and in Fig. 7(b) are the results with AGEI scheme enabled.

The first simulation results are presented in Fig. 7 and illustrate the effectiveness of the AGEI scheme during the autonomous guard events g_{a5} and g_{a6} in pump P_3 . Specifically, in Fig. 7(a), the results of a healthy run are shown where the AGEI scheme is disabled and the autonomous guard events in the hybrid estimator are triggered based on the values of output measurement y_5 . The top plot of Fig. 7(a) shows the mode estimation of pump P_3 (which transitions between modes due to autonomous guard events g_{a5} and g_{a6}) and the bottom plot shows the results for the affected residual in the fault detection scheme. In Fig. 7(b), the same results are shown where this time the AGEI scheme is enabled. As can be seen in 7(b), no false alarms due to the autonomous guard events in the pump are present since AGEI adjust the detection threshold effectively. Moreover, the mode estimation with AGEI enabled is shown to be a lot more effective, since the hybrid estimator switches to the correct mode with only 0.05 – 0.06s delay, while in the case when AGEI is disabled, the hybrid estimator is in a different mode from the system for 3.4 – 13.7s.

Figs. 8-10 present the simulation results when a discrete fault is introduced at 100s, and then a parametric fault is introduced at 200s. Specifically, first, the discrete fault event φ_9 is introduced in the system, which transitions Valve V_1 to a discrete stuck-close fault mode. As can be seen in Fig. 8(a) the discrete fault was

introduced at $t = 100s$. The fault detection scheme quickly detects the fault (see Fig. 8(c)) at $t = 100.05s$, since the residual #1 crosses its corresponding detection threshold, i.e., $r_1 > \bar{R}_1$. Immediately after, the fault isolation scheme is activated, and based on the current estimated mode it determines that 10 fault events out of 16 are possible to have occurred and, thus, employs the corresponding 10 FIEs. As can be seen in Figs. 9(a)-(i), the 9 out of 10 possible fault events are excluded by their corresponding FIEs between $100.46 - 103.83s$ since their residuals exceed their thresholds. For the actual fault event φ_9 , all the components of its FIE (see Figs. 10(a)-(e)) remain below their corresponding threshold, which indicates successful fault isolation at $103.83s$.

Figure 8: Simulation results when a discrete stuck-close fault event φ_9 is introduced in Valve V_1 and then a parametric leak fault φ_1 was introduced in Tank T_1 where: Fig. 8(a) shows Valve V_1 actual and estimated mode, Fig. 8(b) shows Tank T_1 actual and estimated mode, and 8(c) the fault detection scheme.

Later, and while the discrete fault event φ_9 is still present in the system, although isolated as described above, the parametric fault event φ_1 is introduced in the system. The fault event φ_1 transitions Tank T_1 to a parametric leak fault mode with a leak hole value $\theta_1^1 = \rho_1^2 = 25 \text{ mm}^2$. Specifically, and as can be seen in Fig. 8(b), the leak fault is introduced at $t = 200s$. The fault detection scheme quickly detects the fault (see Fig. 8(c)) at $t = 200.05s$ since the residual #1 crosses its corresponding detection threshold, i.e., $r_1 > \bar{R}_1$. Immediately after, the fault isolation scheme is activated, and based on the current estimated mode it determines that 10 fault events out of 16 are possible to have occurred and, thus, employs the corresponding 10 FIEs. As can be seen in Figs. 9(j)-(r), the 9 out of 10 possible fault events are excluded by their corresponding FIEs between $200.77 - 204.84s$, since their residuals exceed their thresholds. For the actual fault event φ_1 , all the components of its FIE (see Figs. 10(f)-(j)) remain below their corresponding thresholds, and hence the fault has successfully been isolated at $204.84s$. Moreover, since this is a parametric fault, the unknown parameter is also approximated by the corresponding FIE, as shown in Fig. 9(k), with $\hat{\theta}_1^1 \approx \theta_1^1 = 25 \text{ mm}^2$.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed an online fault diagnosis approach for a class of nonlinear uncertain hybrid systems. The proposed approach provides effective mode estimation and allows the detection and isolation of both discrete and parametric faults while guaranteeing no false alarms due to modeling uncertainty, measurement noise, and mode mismatches because of autonomous mode transitions.

Specifically, the proposed approach features a hybrid estimation module that models each subsystem individually and the whole system as a composition of these models, making it suitable for large-scale hybrid systems. The fault detection scheme employs a filtering approach that suppresses the measurement noise

Figure 9: Simulation results showing the employed FIEs excluding their corresponding fault events after fault detection. Specifically, Figs. 9(a)-(i) show 9 of the 10 employed FIEs excluding their corresponding fault events after a fault detection at 100.05s. Figs. 9(j)-(r) show 9 of the 10 employed FIEs excluding their corresponding fault events after a fault detection at 200.05s.

Figure 10: Simulation results of all the FIEs components estimating the occurred fault modes after the occurrence of the fault events. Specifically, Figs. 10(a)-(e) show all the components of the FIE estimating the fault mode for the discrete fault event φ_9 , and Figs. 10(f)-(j) show all the components of the FIE estimating the fault mode for the parametric fault event φ_1 . Fig. 10(k) shows the estimation of the unknown parameter θ_1^1 .

and allows the use of tighter thresholds, enhancing the detection of both discrete and parametric faults. An autonomous guard events identification (AGEI) scheme is designed, which identifies the autonomous guard events before they occur and adjusts the threshold in the fault detection scheme accordingly, preventing false alarms due to mode mismatches. Moreover, the AGEI scheme enables effective mode estimation by detecting the occurrence of autonomous guard events in the system and triggering them in the hybrid estimator. Furthermore, the fault isolation scheme dynamically employs fault isolation estimators (FIEs) for only the possible faulty modes and utilizes an exclusion based logic to isolate the occurred fault event. Rigorous analytical results for fault detectability and isolability properties of the proposed approach are also derived. Finally, simulation results of a five tank hybrid testbed system illustrate the effectiveness of the approach. Future research efforts will be devoted making the proposed approach available with fewer measured continuous states and designing a distributed fault diagnosis architecture for uncertain nonlinear systems that will handle sensor faults along with discrete and parametric faults.

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